

Improvement of Mechanical Properties of Composites with Flexible Interphase

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Creating high strength and low scatter materials are kind of dream for material scientist, however, composite materials usually are seemed to be un-reliable material. We have performed tensile tests of unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced composite with large number of specimens because of estimating C.V. values. Table1 shows mean value of tensile strength and C.V. value with various kinds of composites. Also fracture aspects of specimen were observed macroscopically. Apparently, two different fracture aspects led to large scatter as shown in Fig.1. Interphase properties also play important role in this problem, and CF/PPS and CF/PA material good example as shown in Fig.2.

On the other hand, basic mechanical properties of fibre reinforced plastics depend not only on fibre and matrix properties, but also on interfacial properties. Recently, the concept of “interphase” has been recognized. This concept is that interface between fiber and matrix is not surface but a region that has some amount of volume.

In this paper mechanical properties of composites with flexible interphase was described according to interphase concept in order to create reliable composites. Specimens were fabricated by two steps prepreg method, namely flexible epoxy resin was impregnated into fiber bundles first and it was dried in oven. Second impregnated fiber bundles were immersed into normal epoxy resin, and after it was dried for B-stage of resin. Unidirectional composites were fabricated by air-bag fabrication method.

Table1 Tensile properties of unidirectional CFRP laminates

Reinforcing fibre / Matrix resin	Fibre alignment	Tensile strength		Ultimate strain		Elastic modulus		Poisson's ratio					
		N	mean (MPa)	C.V. (%)	N	mean (%)	C.V. (%)	N	mean (-)	C.V. (%)			
M50J / Epoxy		40	2085.5	10.4	37	0.66	7.5	35	313.8	7.3	25	0.296	13.4
M40J / Epoxy		40	2126.1	11.5	35	0.98	12.0	40	226.9	2.9	36	0.315	12.5
MR50 / Epoxy		38	2241.8	13.7	25	1.36	9.8	38	163.1	4.2	36	0.344	9.2
IM400 / Epoxy		39	1964.2	12.5	36	1.23	9.2	39	165.3	9.4	38	0.351	6.4
T300 / #3601		278	1515.3	10.7	276	1.06	9.5	275	138.0	2.1	276	0.334	3.3
T300 / #3631	0°	74	1740.5	6.3	74	1.22	5.2	74	135.5	1.3	74	0.339	2.8
T800 / #3601		79	2518.4	3.0	56	1.45	2.6	77	162.2	1.9	77	0.353	3.3
T800 / #3631		279	2572.7	4.8	244	1.45	3.9	276	165.7	2.8	276	0.349	5.7
AS4 / 1908		85	2132.6	5.6	32	1.39	4.5	34	138.8	2.4	34	0.340	3.7
AS4 / PEEK		83	2253.1	2.4	65	1.55	3.2	87	139.2	1.5	76	0.330	8.7
AT-400 / Nylon 6		100	1511.3	6.2	91	1.28	5.2	93	113.6	3.3	86	0.410	12.4
AT-400 / PPS		15	1560.1	4.7	15	1.31	2.0	15	114.5	2.2	15	0.355	8.7

Fig.1 Typical fracture models of 0degree specimen of T300 &T800 system

Table 2 shows the effects of concentration of flexible resin in first step on tensile strength. 0wt% in this table means normal composites with only brittle epoxy matrix. Tensile strength of 1.0wt% was higher than that of 0wt%, and that of 5.0wt% was lower than 1.0wt% material. Also C.V. value of 1.0wt% material showed the lowest. The fracture aspect of these composites is shown in Fig.3.

Two kinds of fracture aspects were observed in 0wt% material, whereas only brush failure was seen in all composites with flexible interphase. Table3 shows the results of bending test using unidirectional glass fiber reinforced composites. Here again the effects of flexible interphase were confirmed for increasing with strength.

Table2 Tensile properties of CFRP laminates with flexible interphase

Concentration of flexible epoxy resin (wt%)	Fiber alignment	Tensile strength			Ultimate strain			Elastic modulus		
		N	mean (MPa)	C.V. (%)	N	mean (%)	C.V. (%)	N	mean (GPa)	C.V. (%)
0		29	1680.9	5.8	24	1.12	5.0	28	148.8	3.2
0.5	0°	24	1682.3	4.1	23	1.15	4.9	23	147.0	3.8
1.0		26	1727.0	3.7	26	1.24	5.4	25	146.3	4.5
5.0		25	1563.8	3.9	24	1.10	4.3	25	141.7	3.6

Fig.3 Fracture aspects of four type specimens after axial tensile tests